

1 **Resistance that stacks up: Engineering cereals to**
2 **control rust and mildew diseases**

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1 **Abstract**

2 Staying ahead of the arms race against rust and mildew diseases in cereal crops is
3 essential to maintain and preserve food security. The methodological challenges
4 associated with conventional resistance breeding are major bottlenecks for deploying
5 resistance (*R*) genes in high-yielding crop varieties. Advancements in our knowledge
6 of plant genomes, structural mechanisms, innovations in bioinformatics, and improved
7 plant transformation techniques have alleviated this bottleneck by permitting rapid
8 gene isolation, functional studies, directed engineering of synthetic resistance, and
9 precise genome manipulation in elite crop cultivars. Most cloned cereal *R* genes
10 encode canonical immune receptors which, on their own, are prone to being overcome
11 through selection for resistance-evading pathogenic strains. However, the increasingly
12 large repertoire of cloned *R* genes permits multi-gene stacking that, in principle, should
13 provide longer-lasting resistance. This review discusses how these genomics-enabled
14 developments are leading to new breeding and biotechnological opportunities to
15 achieve durable rust and powdery mildew control in cereals.

16 **Keywords:** biotrophic pathogens, genomics, resistance, biotechnology, cereal rusts,
17 powdery mildew

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1 **Introduction**

2 Whole-grain cereals, including wheat (*Triticum* sp.), barley (*Hordeum vulgare*), oat
3 (*Avena sativa*), rye (*Secale cereale*), maize (*Zea mays*), rice (*Oryza sativa*), millet
4 (*Pennisetum glaucum*), and triticale (\times *Triticosecale* Wittmack) are rich sources of
5 calories, essential vitamins, minerals, and phytochemicals that both nourish and
6 protect humans and animals from ailments such as heart attack and cancer (Aune et
7 al., 2016). Of these, wheat is the most widely consumed globally, while barley is the
8 world's fourth most important cereal, used primarily in malt production for alcoholic
9 beverages and as grain feed for livestock and human food (Figure 1; Supplemental
10 Tables 1 and 2). Although cereal cultivation is widespread, global demand and the
11 ability to reliably cultivate large quantities of cereal grain varies substantially between
12 wheat and barley and within different regions of the world worldwide (Figure 1).

13 Cereal grasses are hosts for a myriad of pests and diseases that decrease
14 projected yield and threaten crop production targets (Oerke and Dehne, 2004; Savary
15 et al., 2019). For example, approximately 20% of global wheat production is lost to
16 infection by pests and diseases (Figure 1A). Monoculture and climate change favor
17 the emergence of new, highly virulent pathogen variants that reduce yield, posing a
18 serious threat to global food security (Velásquez et al., 2018). Historically, foliar
19 diseases of cereals have been controlled by (i) eradicating alternate hosts (Barnes et
20 al., 2020), (ii) breeding resistant cultivars (Hafeez et al., 2021), and, more recently, (iii)
21 spraying with systemic fungicides (Deising et al., 2008). Fungicides create selection
22 pressure that encourages the emergence of fungicide-resistant pathogen variants
23 (Tucker et al., 2015). Fungicides are also expensive and can harm humans and the
24 environment. Although genetic resistance has been used to control crop diseases, for
25 example against powdery mildew in wheat and barley (Brown and Wulff, 2022), the

1 durability of the resistance is often limited due to the ability of the pathogen to
2 overcome major race-specific resistance (*R*) genes (McDonald and Linde, 2002).

3 Fungal pathogens that cause disease in cereals and other plants are
4 categorized based on their feeding mechanisms. Biotrophic fungi colonize living plant
5 cells and require carbon and nutrients provided by the host for growth and sporulation
6 (Lorrain et al., 2019). Biotrophic fungal pathogens have a complex biochemical and
7 structural relationship with their hosts (Dracatos et al., 2018). They have evolved
8 specialized structures, called haustoria, that evaginate the host plasma membrane to
9 acquire nutrients and suppress host defenses. Despite sharing similar feeding
10 mechanisms, biotrophic rust and mildew fungi belong to two evolutionarily distinct
11 clades that diverged some 300 million years ago; they are morphologically distinctive,
12 differ by the host cells they infect, and employ different methods of colonization (Aim
13 et al., 2018; Naranjo-Ortiz and Gabaldón, 2019). Biotrophic fungi create a nutrient sink
14 surrounding the infection site, which affects the host ability to supply nutrients to its
15 own sink organs, such as grain in the case of cereal crops (Lorrain et al., 2019). By
16 contrast, necrotrophic fungi acquire nutrients from dead plant tissue. Rather than
17 relying on haustoria, necrotrophic fungi tend to overpower their hosts with a cocktail
18 of virulence factors and secreted molecules (Voegelé and Mendgen, 2003; Koeck et
19 al., 2011).

20 The initial recognition of non-self or pathogen-associated molecular patterns
21 (PAMPs) and subsequent mounting of downstream defense responses by plants
22 occur at the cell surface by membrane-associated or pathogen recognition receptors
23 (PRRs) and are collectively referred to as PAMP-triggered immunity (PTI). Adapted
24 biotrophic pathogens have co-evolved with their hosts and consequently produce

1 effectors that enable them to evade PTI, colonize surrounding cells, and cause
2 disease. The multilayered immune system from the host plant comprises large gene
3 families encoding membrane-bound and intracellular receptor proteins that recognize
4 race-specific pathogen effector molecules, leading to effector-triggered immunity (ETI)
5 (Oliver 2009; Dodds and Rathjen, 2010; Spoel and Dong, 2012). Our understanding
6 of the genes involved in host-biotrophic pathogen interactions is advanced, especially
7 for common *R* genes encoding nucleotide-binding leucine-rich repeat (NLR) proteins.
8 The products of other non-canonical *R* genes underscore a level of mechanistic
9 diversification that is less well understood (Sánchez-Martín and Keller, 2021);
10 however, in combination with NLRs, they are likely to provide a formidable barrier for
11 pathogens to overcome (Brun et al., 2010).

12 New genomic approaches have enhanced the rate of gene isolation, improving
13 our understanding of the molecular basis of host disease resistance and acquisition of
14 virulence by the pathogen. In the case of biotrophic pathogens that infect economically
15 important crop species, this molecular insight has been facilitated by an in-depth
16 knowledge of host-pathogen genetics for each of the respective pathosystems. Cereal
17 rust (*Puccinia* spp.) and mildew (*Blumeria* spp.) pathogens are highly host-specific,
18 having co-evolved with a narrow range of host species (Dracatos et al., 2018). Among
19 *Puccinia* species, those that attack wheat are the most economically important (Savary
20 et al., 2019). Stem rust, an epiphytotic disease caused by *P. graminis* f. sp. *tritici* (*Pgt*),
21 can lead to crop failure during heavy epidemics, while stripe rust, caused by *P.*
22 *striiformis* f. sp. *tritici* (*Pst*), and leaf rust, caused by *P. triticina* (*Pt*), cause losses of up
23 to 50% on susceptible varieties. For the mildew fungus *B. graminis*, the pathogenic
24 strains adapted to wheat (f. sp. *tritici*), or barley (f. sp. *hordei*) cause the most economic
25 losses (Conner et al., 2003; Everts et al., 2001). In this review, we discuss recent

1 developments in the molecular genetic analysis of wheat and barley interactions with
2 rust- and powdery mildew-causing fungi and explore opportunities to engineer durable
3 host resistance.

4 **Capturing functional diversity through genomics-enhanced association** 5 **genetics**

6 The availability of reference genomes and the development of gene-class-specific
7 capture arrays have undoubtedly enhanced *R* gene cloning efforts using map-based
8 cloning (Klymiuk et al., 2018; Walkowiak et al., 2020), mutational genomics (Sánchez-
9 Martín et al., 2016; Steuernagel et al., 2016), and genome-wide association studies
10 (GWAS) (Arora et al., 2019). Moreover, unbiased complexity reduction approaches,
11 such as TACCA (targeted chromosome-based cloning via long-range assembly) or
12 MutChromSeq, that are based on chromosome sorting and sequencing of wild type
13 plants and chemically induced mutants have been applied to isolating genes involved
14 in disease resistance (Sánchez-Martín et al., 2016; Thind et al., 2017; Dracatos et al.,
15 2019; Yu et al., 2022a) and morphological characteristics (Ford et al., 2018) in cereals.
16 A highly efficient approach combining PacBio Iso-Seq of the wild-type parental
17 genotype with RNA sequencing of multiple mutants was used to clone the wheat leaf
18 rust *R* gene *Lr9*. This approach substantially decreased the cost and time of gene
19 cloning, mitigating the necessity to sort chromosomes, and is highly amenable for non-
20 reference wheat *R* gene donor lines (Wang et al., 2022). The necessity for genome
21 complexity reduction methodology is decreasing as researchers capitalize more on
22 the rapidly declining costs of DNA sequencing to generate reference genomes of
23 resistant accessions (Athiyannan et al., 2022; Yu et al., 2022b; Li et al., 2022) or
24 sequence genetically diverse panels for GWAS (Gaurav et al., 2022).

1 Mining germplasm collections for traits of interest and introducing them into crop
2 breeding programs is far from novel. Fundamental to this activity are the tens of
3 thousands of crop accessions maintained in global gene banks along with passport
4 data (a basic description of the accession such as accession name, genus, country of
5 origin, acquisition date, etc.). However, errors in labeling can lead to duplications
6 (Singh et al., 2019). Milner and colleagues generated molecular passport data by
7 performing genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS) on the entire German *ex situ* gene bank
8 of more than 23,000 accessions of wild and domesticated barley (Milner et al., 2019).
9 This resource provided insight into the global population structure of domesticated
10 barley and, through increased marker density and population size, greater analytical
11 power for GWAS. Furthermore, phenotyping diverse subsets of the barley gene bank
12 identified marker-trait associations underlying previously cloned genes controlling
13 virus resistance and morphological traits (Milner et al., 2019). In a separate study,
14 whole-genome shotgun sequencing of 242 diverse Tausch's goatgrass (*Aegilops*
15 *tauschii*) accessions revealed that the D genome of wheat was sourced from
16 geographically distinct lineages, while GWAS identified and validated candidate genes
17 underlying stem rust (*SrTA1662*) and powdery mildew (*WTK4*, [*WHEAT TANDEM*
18 *PROTEIN KINASE4*]) *R* genes (Gaurav et al., 2022). These approaches facilitate rapid
19 identification of previously uncharacterized alleles for resistance to biotrophic fungal
20 pathogens in cereal crops.

21 **Pan-genomics reveal the extent of variation at R loci**

22 Molecular passport data can be used to select representative genotypes suitable for
23 sequencing and assembling chromosome-scale reference genomes. Pan-genome
24 projects in bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) (Walkowiak et al., 2020) and barley

1 (Jayakodi et al., 2020) have unraveled the extent of intraspecies structural variation
2 on both micro and macro scales. The availability of a pan-genome addresses the most
3 common bottleneck in gene cloning projects, which is over-reliance on gene order and
4 representation in a single available reference genome. In the case of the barley pan-
5 genome, representative barley genotypes were selected from each of the major global
6 gene pools based on the GBS data from 23,000 barley accessions reported in Milner
7 et al., (2019). Further selection criteria were imposed to maximize geographical
8 diversity including row type and growth habit. The utility of the barley and wheat pan-
9 genomes lies in being able to use the information from the most closely related
10 genotype or directly from the sequenced genotype harboring the trait of interest as a
11 reference genome, thus limiting the number of single nucleotide polymorphisms
12 (SNPs), presence/absence variations (PAVs), and inversions.

13 Gene duplication and diversifying selection have given rise to a clustered
14 distribution of NLRs in plant genomes (Lee and Chae, 2020). Pan-genome variants,
15 such as PAVs, are especially relevant for NLRs and other types of *R* genes. Often, the
16 NLR conditioning the resistance is absent or has reduced functionality in susceptible
17 accessions, e.g., due to a premature stop codon (Sánchez-Martín et al., 2016). A
18 bread wheat pan-genome study illustrated this point when examining NLR gene
19 expansion in the genome assemblies of eight diverse elite wheat cultivars, the Chinese
20 Spring landrace, and spelt wheat (*Triticum spelta*) (Walkowiak et al., 2020). A *de novo*
21 annotation of their NLR complements identified, on average, 2,500 full-length NLR loci
22 per accession. Only 31–34% of the NLR signatures were shared across all 10
23 genomes and the number of unique NLRs ranged from 22 to 192 per genome. The
24 total NLR complement of all 10 wheat lines consisted of 5,905 (98% identity) to 7,780
25 (100% identity) unique NLRs. Furthermore, the authors estimated that 90% of the NLR

1 complement was reached at between eight (considering 95% sequence identity) and
2 11 wheat lines (considering 100% protein sequence identity). These findings highlight
3 the size and complexity of the wheat immune receptor complement, the extent of PAVs
4 between accessions, and the dynamic evolution of the plant immune system
5 (Walkowiak et al., 2020).

6 The releases of the wheat and barley pan-genomes have already been and will
7 continue to be important for isolating non-canonical *R* genes. For example, two recent
8 studies utilized sequenced chromosome-scale assemblies from the wheat and barley
9 pan-genomes to clone the broad-spectrum leaf rust *R* genes *Leaf rust 14a* (*Lr14a*)
10 (Kolodziej et al., 2021) and *Resistance to Puccinia hordei 3* (*Rph3*) (Dinh et al., 2022)
11 from wheat and barley, respectively. *Lr14a* and *Rph3* encode an ankyrin membrane-
12 bound repeat protein and a putative executor protein, respectively, which are race-
13 specific non-canonical resistance proteins. In the case of *Rph3*, identification of a large
14 80-kb deletion in the resistant barley cv. Barke relative to the reference genome
15 assembly of the susceptible cv. Morex delimited the candidate locus to two possible
16 genes (Dinh et al., 2022). Similarly, cloning and characterization of *R* genes encoding
17 kinase fusion proteins, such as *Resistance to Puccinia graminis 1* (*Rpg1*)
18 (Brueggeman et al., 2002), *Yellow rust resistance 15* (*Yr15*) (Klymiuk et al., 2018), *Lr9*
19 (Wang et al., 2022), *Stem rust resistance 43* (*Sr43*) (Yu et al., 2022a), *Sr60* (Chen et
20 al., 2020), *Sr62* (Yu et al., 2022b), *WTK4* (Gaurav et al., 2021), *Powdery mildew*
21 *resistance 4* (*Pm4*) (Sánchez-Martín et al., 2021), *Pm21* (He et al., 2018), and *Rwt4*
22 (synonym of *Resistance to Magnaporthe grisea 1* (*Rmg1*) (Arora et al., 2022), along
23 with the Kolodziej et al., 2021 and Dinh et al., 2022 studies suggest that as many as
24 35% of major, dominant, race-specific *R* genes to biotrophic pathogens of wheat and
25 barley do not encode canonical NLR immune receptors (Supplemental Table 3).

1 Improvements to long-read sequencing technologies continue to enhance our
2 ability to generate ultra-contiguous chromosome-scale assemblies, thus further
3 improving the efficacy of *R* gene identification. Athiyannan and colleagues combined
4 PacBio high-fidelity long reads, optical mapping, and chromosome conformation
5 capture (HiC) to generate an improved 14.7-Gb chromosome-scale assembly of the
6 South African stripe rust-resistant bread wheat cv. Kariega (Athiyannan et al., 2022).
7 These authors improved the N₅₀ contig length previously reported for both short-read
8 and PacBio long-read sequencing technologies by 150- to 600-fold, to 30.22 Mb. The
9 improved genome assembly permitted efficient isolation of the race-specific *R* gene
10 *Yr27*. Taken together, these wheat and barley pan-genome studies highlight
11 opportunities to accelerate the cloning and characterization of *R* genes. To maximize
12 the potential of pan-genomes and sequenced germplasm diversity panels, it will be
13 critical to determine their *R* gene complements by performing detailed multi-pathotype
14 testing using diverse rust and mildew isolates with contrasting pathogenicity profiles.
15 This comprehensive analysis will help determine the presence of previously identified
16 genes, allowing promising accessions to be shortlisted for preliminary genetic analysis
17 to map novel *R* loci.

18 **NLR integrated domains reveal the diversity of pathogenicity targets in ETI**

19 NLRs are immune receptor proteins that typically contain three domains. The central
20 nucleotide-binding domain is common to all NLRs. Most NLRs also have a C-terminal
21 leucine-rich repeat (LRR) domain, which confers pathogen recognition specificity, and
22 an N-terminal interaction domain involved in signaling and subsequent cell death
23 (Duxbury et al., 2020). In monocots (all cereal species), the N terminus typically
24 contains a coiled coil (CC) domain. By contrast, dicots have either a CC domain or a

1 toll interleukin receptor (TIR) domain. Recent NLR gene cloning and functional studies
2 have unraveled a diverse array of atypical integrated domains (IDs) that act as decoys
3 for pathogen effectors and trigger a specific immune reaction when interacting with the
4 decoy (Marchal et al., 2022). Examples include zinc-finger (ZF), BED, and WRKY
5 domains of transcription factors, which are common targets for effector proteins as
6 they play a crucial role in regulating signal transduction during basal plant immunity
7 (Sarris et al., 2016). In some cases, NLR genes encode immune receptor proteins with
8 ID combinations that are species-specific or are common across different cereal and
9 crop species. Map-based cloning of the stripe rust *R* gene *YrU1* from red wild einkorn
10 wheat (*Triticum urartu*) revealed that it encodes a CC-NBS-LRR protein with an N-
11 terminal ankyrin-repeat (ANK) domain and a C-terminal WRKY domain (ANK-NLR-
12 WRKY). Further empirical searches determined that this unusual NLR protein
13 structure is only found in *Triticum* species (Wang et al., 2020).

14 The ZF-BED domain was originally characterized in the fruit fly (*Drosophila*
15 *melanogaster*) through mutagenesis studies and was subsequently shown to be
16 essential for *Xa1*-mediated resistance to bacterial blight in rice (Yoshimura et al.,
17 1998). In bread wheat, two BED domain containing NLRs (*Yr5* and *Yr7*), encoded by
18 a complex NLR gene cluster with unique pathogen specificity, confer resistance to
19 stripe rust (Marchal et al., 2018). The discovery that the barley leaf rust *R* gene *Rph15*
20 also encodes an NLR-BED domain-containing protein suggests that different rust
21 pathogen species that are adapted to distinct hosts may have effectors targeting
22 similar transcription factor domains (Chen et al., 2021). Functional studies in other
23 plant species demonstrated that the binding of effectors with IDs can activate plant
24 defense. The WRKY domain of RESISTANT TO RALSTONIA SOLANACEARUM 1
25 (RRS1), an NLR from *Arabidopsis* (*Arabidopsis thaliana*), is an integrated decoy that

1 is targeted by two effector proteins from different pathogens whose binding activates
2 RRS1-mediated resistance (Sarris et al., 2015). Analogously, the NLR proteins RGA5
3 and Pik-1 from rice contain heavy metal-associated (HMA) domains that act as a
4 decoy for effectors of the rice blast pathogen *Magnaporthe oryzae* (Guo et al., 2018).
5 De la Concepcion et al., (2019) engineered a variant of Pik-1 (Pik1h) with a single
6 amino acid substitution in the HMA domain that broadens its recognition specificity to
7 corresponding Avr-Pik effectors. Increasing our understanding of the diversity of IDs
8 within cereal NLR proteins will broaden our toolkit for engineering resistance to
9 biotrophic pathogens such as rusts and mildews.

10 **Diverse ‘gatekeepers’ of host specialization**

11 Proteins encoded by structurally distinct *R* gene classes have key roles in forming host
12 specificity barriers. A pertinent example is in wheat, where the two neighboring *R*
13 genes *Rwt3* and *Rwt4*, encoding an NLR and a tandem kinase, respectively, act as
14 host-specificity barriers against non-*Triticum* blast pathotypes (Arora et al., 2022). In
15 *Hordeum* spp., orthologous cell wall-associated receptor kinase genes from cultivated
16 (*H. vulgare*) and bulbous (*H. bulbosum*) barley conferred both partial and non-host
17 resistance to adapted and non-adapted leaf rust pathogens, respectively (Wang et al.,
18 2019). The partial-resistance quantitative trait locus (QTL) *Rphq2* (*Resistance to P.*
19 *hordei 2*) from Dutch barley cv. Vada confers quantitative resistance to adapted strains
20 of the leaf rust pathogen *P. hordei* and nonhost resistance to leaf rust strains adapted
21 to bulbous barley. In parallel, *Rph22* from *H. bulbosum*, which maps to the same
22 physical position as *Rphq2*, confers partial resistance to *P. bulbosii* and nonhost
23 resistance to *P. hordei*. Positional cloning and phenotypic validation of each
24 orthologous kinase in a susceptible transgenic background determined that *Rphq2*

1 and *Rph22* both conferred a stronger nonhost resistance response to heterologous
2 leaf rust pathogens relative to the partial response to their respective adapted leaf rust
3 pathogens (Wang et al., 2019). The authors subsequently hypothesized that leaf rust
4 isolates adapted to cultivated (*P. hordei*) and bulbous (*P. bulbosii*) barley had co-
5 evolved with their respective hosts to mitigate perception by host receptors by lowering
6 ligand recognition.

7 Shared genetic architecture of *R* loci within and between closely related cereal
8 genomes is often characterized by diverse pathogen specificity. The *Mla* (*mildew*
9 *resistance locus a*) clade on the short arm of chromosome 1H in barley is exemplified
10 by its pronounced allelic diversification (Jørgensen 1994). Recent phylogenetic
11 analysis of the wheat stem rust R proteins Sr33 and Sr50 showed them to be orthologs
12 of barley *Mla* proteins based on amino acid similarity to *Mla1*, *Mla6*, and *Mla9*, and
13 shared synteny between the group 1 chromosomes within the Triticeae (Dracatos et
14 al., 2019). This observation suggests that, although evolving from a common ancestor,
15 NLRs from the *Mla* clade have evolved distinct resistance specificities to different
16 biotrophic fungi both within and between respective crop species. In some instances,
17 however, NLRs can have dual-pathogen recognition specificities conferring race-
18 specific resistance to adapted pathogens and resistance to pathogen variants adapted
19 to closely related host species. For instance, a 522-bp region of the sequence
20 encoding the LRR domain within *Mla8* determines dual specificity for recognizing
21 barley powdery mildew and wheat stripe rust (Bettgenhaeuser et al., 2021). *Mla8*
22 represents a striking example of the shared genetic architecture within cereal
23 genomes for resistance to both adapted and non-adapted biotrophic pathogens of
24 different genera, implicating this *R* gene in host species specificity to the wheat stripe
25 rust pathogen. Barley is a host to adapted *P. striiformis* strains; however, *Mla8* did not

1 confer resistance to the *P. striiformis* f. sp. *hordei* isolates tested. These two studies
2 emphasize the importance of further molecular characterization and understanding to
3 be able to manipulate nonhost resistance traits in cereal crops for biotechnological
4 applications. In parallel, understanding the molecular signatures of host specificity
5 between biotrophic pathogen isolates specialized to closely related host cereal
6 grasses (*formae speciales*) using pathogenomics may help predict future host jumps.

7 **Utilizing cloned avirulence genes to confirm function and predict NLR gene** 8 **durability**

9 Cloning the pathogen effectors corresponding to broadly effective individual race-
10 specific *R* genes will play an important role in determining *R* gene function. Compared
11 to the 70 *R* genes cloned from *Triticum* and *Hordeum* spp. (including 42 NLRs), only
12 18 corresponding avirulence genes encoding secreted pathogen effectors have been
13 cloned (Supplemental Tables 3 and 4). This research field has lagged that of *R* gene
14 cloning due to the challenges of working with obligate biotrophic fungal pathogens.
15 However, going forward, the large number of cloned *R* genes combined with recent
16 progress in developing transient expression systems (Lorrain et al., 2019) will facilitate
17 effector biology studies by permitting rapid functional assays to study their specificity.

18 Other major drivers include recent advancements in sequencing technologies,
19 such as PacBio SMRT sequencing and chromosome conformation capture
20 sequencing (Hi-C), which have enabled haplo-phasing of dikaryotic rust genomes to
21 increase assembly quality (Schwessinger et al., 2018; Duan et al., 2022). Numerous
22 avirulence genes were previously cloned in the flax rust (*Melampsora lini*)
23 experimental system; however, to date, only three *Avr* genes have been characterized

1 from the wheat stem rust pathogen *Pgt*: *AvrSr35* (Salcedo et al., 2017), *AvrSr50* (Chen
2 et al., 2017), and most recently *AvrSr27* (Upadhyaya et al., 2021).

3 One mechanism contributing to the breakdown of rust resistance through loss of
4 avirulence in pathogen populations is the proliferation and mobilization of transposable
5 elements within rust pathogen genomes. For instance, transposon-mediated
6 disruption of *AvrSr35* resulted in natural *Sr35*-virulent *Pgt* isolates (Salcedo et al.,
7 2017). Loss of avirulence can also occur via large-scale chromosomal changes in
8 pathogen genomes. For example, in the case of *AvrSr50*, a spontaneous deletion-
9 mutant was identified, which allowed the identification of *AvrSr50* by comparative
10 sequence analysis (Chen et al., 2017). The crystal structure of a natural *AvrSr50*
11 variant was recently solved, which showed structural similarity to cupin-like proteins
12 with a carbohydrate binding domain. Subsequently, site-directed mutagenesis and
13 transient expression assays were used to understand the potential mechanisms
14 conferring the gain of virulence. *AvrSr50* mutants escaped recognition by the stem
15 rust resistance receptor *Sr50* by means of DNA insertion or stop codon loss in
16 *AvrSr50*, or via a single amino acid substitution of the surface-exposed residue Q121
17 in the *AvrSr50* protein (Ortiz et al., 2022). Furthermore, a recent study determined the
18 key residues in the LRR domain of *Sr50* responsible for the recognition of,
19 autoactivation of, and interaction with *AvrSr50* by performing cell death assays in *T.*
20 *aestivum* protoplasts and *Nicotiana benthamiana* leaves. These same authors
21 engineered *Sr33* from Tausch's goatgrass (*Aegilops tauschii*), which shares 80%
22 similarity at the protein level with *Sr50*, to recognize *AvrSr50* (Tamborski et al., 2022).
23 These studies represent important steps toward understanding and monitoring rust
24 pathogen evolution while providing avenues for *R* gene engineering in grasses.

1 The generation of haplo-phased reference assemblies for cereal rust isolates has
2 enabled several recent breakthroughs in cereal rust pathogenomics and effector
3 biology (Duan et al., 2022; Henningsen et al., 2022). A genome assembly of the highly
4 avirulent *Pgt* isolate 21-0 led to the cloning of *AvrSr27* and the discovery that the Ug99
5 stem rust isolate is a somatic hybrid of two *Pgt* isolates (Li et al., 2019; Upadhyaya et
6 al., 2021). In the case of *AvrSr27*, virulence for *Sr27* could be achieved experimentally
7 or occur within the field via deletion mutations, copy number variation, and expression
8 level polymorphisms (Upadhyaya et al., 2021). The recent generation of a second
9 reference assembly of the Ug99 strain of *Pgt* enabled researchers to demonstrate that
10 somatic hybridization was due to nuclei exchange between 21-0 and an
11 uncharacterized *Pgt* isolate of African origin. Further haplotype analysis of neighboring
12 *AvrSr35* and *AvrSr50* avirulence genes revealed that both are heterozygous in the
13 Ug99 founder lineage, highlighting the potential for single-step mutations in the
14 pathogen to overcome their corresponding cloned, effective stem rust *R* genes (Li et
15 al., 2019). This information validates the utility of Avr gene cloning studies to forecast
16 the durability of deployed NLR genes and to confirm the function of stacked race-
17 specific *R* genes. Further information on the effectiveness of the different cereal rust
18 and mildew *R* genes cloned to date is detailed in Supplemental Tables 5-9 and
19 summarized in Figure 2 to inform potential future inclusion for pyramiding in gene
20 stacks. The relative effectiveness of each cloned *R* gene is based on published
21 phenotypic response data collected using diverse rust and mildew pathogen isolates
22 from international cereal disease laboratories.

23 **Altering the success of biotrophy utilizing naturally occurring recessive**
24 **mutations**

1 Although rare in nature, recessively inherited non-lethal loss-of-function mutations can
2 spontaneously occur within “susceptibility” (S) genes that regulate and facilitate the
3 biotrophic feeding habit of rust and mildew pathogens (van Schie et al., 2014). Recent
4 fundamental research into plant transporter proteins have associated their
5 mechanisms with yield enhancement and tolerance to biotic and abiotic stresses (Peck
6 and Mittler, 2020). Due to the polyploid genome of bread wheat, spontaneous loss-of-
7 function mutations are either tolerated or their effect is masked by functionally
8 redundant gene homeologs (Krasileva et al., 2017). Loss-of-function mutations in S
9 genes derived from polyploid species, such as bread wheat, confer pleiotropic
10 resistance to multiple biotrophic pathogen genera and species. However, these are
11 often accompanied by deleterious yield penalty traits. The best examples of loss-of-
12 function pleiotropic resistance are two cloned partial-resistance genes,
13 *Lr34/Yr18/Sr57/Pm18* (Krattinger et al., 2009) and *Lr67/Yr46/Sr55/Pm46/Ltn3* (Moore
14 et al., 2015), from bread wheat that encode ABC and hexose transporters,
15 respectively. These two cloned *R* alleles plus a third locus, *Lr46/Yr29/Sr58/Pm39*, are
16 also associated with leaf tip necrosis that has a minor yield penalty (Rosewarne et al.,
17 2006). Despite this penalty, breeding programs can minimize yield losses in the
18 presence of *Lr34*. For example, introducing *Lr34* into the wheat cv. Thatcher caused
19 a 15% decrease in yield in fungicide-treated trials (Drijepont et al., 1990), whereas the
20 presence of *Lr34* caused only a 6% yield loss in CIMMYT wheat cultivars (Singh and
21 Huerta-Espino, 1997), likely because of many cycles of selection in the CIMMYT
22 breeding program.

23 Major advances have been made in our understanding of the molecular basis of
24 disease resistance in crops, facilitating informed gene editing opportunities. The utility
25 in gene editing also lies in the exploitation of comparative genomics between crop
17

1 species. *S* genes often encode nutrient transporters or enzymes that are well
2 conserved at the amino acid level, especially between closely related crop species
3 such as wheat and barley. However, comparative genomics may be less effective
4 when editing *S* genes in wheat derived from more distant relatives such as rice. A
5 functional analysis of the Lr67res protein from *T. aestivum* using frog oocytes and
6 yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) determined the presence of a sugar-independent
7 anion influx occurring in Lr67res but not in the Lr67sus natural variant, suggesting a
8 potential gain-of-function mutation. Furthermore, leaf tip necrosis was enhanced by
9 NaCl treatment, suggesting an altered nutritional status of the plant that is associated
10 with, yet likely decoupled from, the mutations inducing resistance (Milne et al., 2022).
11 The effects observed in frog eggs and yeast were also observed in plants. Using site-
12 directed mutagenesis, the equivalent two residues that differentiate Lr67sus and
13 Lr67res were introduced into the orthologous barley sugar transporter (STP13) and
14 then transformed into the leaf rust susceptible cv. Golden Promise (Milne et al., 2019).
15 While the collective presence of both amino acid variants conferred resistance to
16 barley leaf rust accompanied by leaf tip necrosis, only one variant (G144A) was
17 sufficient to confer sensitivity to NaCl (Milne et al., 2022).

18 Protein kinases have important roles in conferring race-specific and broad-
19 spectrum resistance to biotrophic fungal diseases in wheat (Klymiuk et al., 2018; Wang
20 et al., 2022a; Yu et al., 2022) and barley (Brueggeman et al., 2002; Wang et al., 2019).
21 Most of these studies involved specific tandem or wall-associated kinases being
22 inherited as dominant *R* genes. By contrast, a recent study in bread wheat suggested
23 that a Ser/Thr kinase gene, *Puccinia striiformis-Induced Protein Kinase 1* (*TaPsIPK1*),
24 acts as an *S* gene. The authors cloned the *Pst* effector gene encoding PsSpg1, which
25 targets and binds to TaPsIPK1, and showed that autophosphorylation and nuclear

1 translocation of TaPsIPK1 is required for *Pst* virulence. The subsequent TaPsIPK1-
2 dependent phosphorylation of the transcription factor C-REPEAT/DRE BINDING
3 FACTOR 1d (TaCBF1d) regulated gene expression in the nucleus; however,
4 disruption of all three *TaPsIPK1* homoeologs led to a primed host immune response
5 conferring broad-spectrum resistance. A field assessment using geographically
6 defined pathogen isolates and environmental conditions did not reveal any deleterious
7 effects associated with disrupting *TaPsIPK1* via gene editing. This study highlights the
8 ability to target multiple classes of *S* genes as by gene editing to improve resistance
9 and to enhance our understanding of host-pathogen interactions (Wang et al., 2022b).

10 On average, a greater proportion of rust and mildew *R* genes are recessive in
11 barley (26%) relative to polyploid wheat (6.7%), likely because of redundancy between
12 homeologous genes in wheat (Uauy et al., 2017). The most notable example is *mlo*-
13 mediated resistance in barley to the powdery mildew fungus that has remained
14 effective for over 50 years after its introduction into agriculture (Kusch and Panstruga,
15 2017). *mlo* resistance is derived from loss-of-function mutations in *Mlo* encoding a
16 serpentine plasma membrane protein (Panstruga, 2005). The mechanism of
17 resistance remains poorly understood, but *mlo* protein accumulates at powdery mildew
18 microdomain infection sites that modulate cell actin cytoskeleton arrangement (Bhat
19 et al., 2005). Several barley *mlo* alleles trigger a developmentally controlled defense
20 mimic phenotype affecting yield; however, unlike the *Lr34/Yr18/Sr57/Pm18*,
21 *Lr46/Yr29/Sr58/Pm39*, and *Lr67/Yr46/Sr55/Pm46/Ltn3* pleiotropic partial-resistance
22 genes characterized in wheat, there is no evidence that any of the *mlo* alleles confer
23 resistance to barley rust diseases.

1 The adverse effects of *mlo* mutations, such as premature leaf senescence, are
2 well documented and are consistent with Mlo having a broad role in delaying or
3 preventing mesophyll cell death in pathogen-challenged and non-challenged leaves
4 (Piffanelli et al., 2002; Consonni et al., 2006). However, Li and co-authors found that
5 a 304-kb deletion mutant (Tamlo-R32) at the wheat *Mlo* B-genome locus, originally
6 edited to create *mlo* alleles in wheat, did not result in the growth defects observed in
7 other wheat *mlo* mutants. The absence of the *mlo*-related yield defects was not due to
8 a deletion in the protein coding region of *Mlo* but rather to de-repression of the
9 neighboring gene *Tonoplast Monosaccharide Transporter 3 (TaTMT3B)*. *TaTMT3B* is
10 normally silenced in wild-type wheat, but the large adjacent deletion altered the local
11 chromatin structure leading to its de-repression (Li et al., 2022). These desirable
12 effects were confirmed using elite wheat cultivars under field conditions in China, and
13 in the model species *Arabidopsis*. The study by Li et al., 2022 provides a crucial
14 gateway to improve the utilization of *mlo*-induced resistance in cereals, other grasses,
15 and, by extrapolation from the *Arabidopsis* results, in other vegetable and horticultural
16 food crops susceptible to powdery mildew (Spanu, 2022; Brown and Wulff, 2022).

17 **Gene stacks utilizing mechanistic diversity**

18 The central dogma of pyramiding *R* genes states that as the number of genes
19 introgressed, transformed, or bred into a cereal variety increase, the more challenging
20 it will be for pathogen populations to evolve corresponding virulence to multiple
21 resistance components. Pyramiding *R* genes using transgenic and cisgenic
22 biotechnological approaches was successful for conditioning complete late blight
23 (*Phytophthora infestans*) resistance in potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) (Song et al.,
24 2003). The *Lr34/Yr18/Sr57/Pm18* ABC transporter gene was transferred using

1 transgenesis directly into several cereal crops including durum wheat (*T. durum*;
2 Rinaldo et al., 2017), barley (Risk et al., 2013), and rice (Krattinger et al., 2016) with
3 varying success. Severe deleterious effects, including senescence, were observed in
4 diploid barley and rice transgenic lines expressing *Lr34*, whereas in the tetraploid
5 durum wheat, *Lr34* induced seedling resistance to leaf rust, stripe rust, and powdery
6 mildew (Rinaldo et al., 2017). This finding suggests that the deleterious effects
7 worsened at reduced ploidy levels, which may be a feature of genes with pleiotropic
8 functions in their endogenous polyploid background. By contrast, the cloned wheat
9 NLR genes *Sr22*, *Sr33*, *Sr35*, and *Sr45* confer race-specific resistance to *Pgt* when
10 transformed into barley cv. Golden Promise without any noticeable agronomic effect
11 (Hatta et al., 2021).

12 Taking advantage of technological developments in vector construction and the
13 availability of a suite of cloned stem rust *R* genes, a stack comprising five distinct
14 cloned *R* genes was transferred into bread wheat. The stack, referred to as the 'Big
15 Five', comprises the cloned *Lr67/Yr46/Sr55/Pm46* partial-resistance gene and the all-
16 stage stem rust *R* genes *Sr22*, *Sr35*, *Sr45*, and *Sr50*, and has been rigorously
17 assessed for effectiveness in response to diverse global races of *Pgt*. In the T₁
18 progeny of three transgenic lines all five full-length genes were inherited as a single
19 locus confirming the co-insertion of each gene. The *R* genes were transformed into
20 the rust-susceptible bread wheat cv. Fielder and, although conferring complete
21 immunity to seven highly virulent global *Pgt* isolates, the transgenic seedlings were
22 susceptible to leaf and stripe rust (Luo et al., 2021). This study highlights the
23 effectiveness of pyramiding four highly effective race-specific NLRs with an additional
24 partial-resistance gene to control stem rust. The technology also demonstrates the
25 opportunity to introduce multiple genes and/or stacks of genes into the same cultivar
21

1 and design either disease-specific or multi-disease *R* gene stacks containing different
2 gene combinations for durable disease control in wheat and barley. Based on the
3 available rust *R* genes cloned to date in wheat, Figure 2C depicts disease-specific
4 gene stacks that reflect a diverse mechanistic action and broad efficacy to the three
5 rust pathogens of wheat. The cloned pleiotropic genes *Lr34/Yr18/Sr57/Pm18* and
6 *Lr67/Yr46/Sr55/Pm46* were included in the leaf rust and stem rust stacks, respectively.
7 These genes provide incomplete yet broad spectrum resistance to powdery mildew,
8 redressing the reduced efficacy of cloned mildew *R* genes across the different regions
9 in the world (Supplemental Tables 8 and 9). Moreover, *Lr34/Yr18/Sr57/Pm18* and
10 *Lr67/Yr46/Sr55/Pm46* can potentiate race specific rust resistance genes (McCallum
11 and Hiebert 2022), thus likely improving the overall effectiveness of the stacks.

12 **Innovative approaches to improve transformation efficiency**

13 The recalcitrance of crop plants to *Agrobacterium* (*Agrobacterium tumefaciens*)-
14 mediated transformation (ABMT) was, until recently, arguably the largest bottleneck
15 limiting progress in plant biotechnology. This recalcitrance is largely due to the high
16 frequency of host-*Agrobacterium* incompatibility explained by strong plant-induced
17 defense responses and that *Agrobacterium* is predominantly adapted to infect dicot
18 plants. The genetic basis of ABMT efficiency in plants is complex and strongly
19 genotype-dependent. Several QTLs have been mapped in *Brassica oleracea* (Cogan
20 et al., 2004) and barley (Hisano et al., 2017) permitting a haplotype-based assessment
21 and selection for improved ABMT efficiency.

22 The options available to improve transformation efficiency are to isolate and
23 manipulate the causal genes underlying ABMT, explore approaches to improve ABMT,
24 or devise alternative transformation systems. One approach to improve ABMT

1 involves engineering *Agrobacterium* to express a type III secretion system and deliver
2 the effectors *AvrPto*, *AvrPtoB*, or *HopA01* derived from the tomato (*Solanum*
3 *lycopersicum*) pathogen *Pseudomonas syringae* to suppress plant defense. This
4 technology increased ABMT efficiency by 250–400% across the diverse plant species
5 wheat, alfalfa (*Medicago sativa*), and switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) (Raman et al.,
6 2022). The system also permits direct delivery of a plant histone protein into somatic
7 plant cells in a non-transgenic manner to enhance ABMT efficiency. Enhancements in
8 ABMT efficiency have also been demonstrated in monocot species using morphogenic
9 regulation. Expression of a construct encoding a fusion protein combining wheat
10 GROWTH-REGULATING FACTOR 4 (GRF4) and its cofactor GRF-INTERACTING
11 FACTOR 1 (GIF1) substantially increased ABMT efficiency and regeneration speed in
12 monocots and dicots (Debernardi et al., 2020). Overexpressing *Baby boom* and
13 *Wuschel* improved ABMT in previously recalcitrant maize inbred lines and improved
14 transformation frequencies in sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) immature embryos and in
15 rice callus (Lowe et al., 2016). These morphogenic enhancers could, in principle, be
16 delivered via an *Agrobacterium* strain expressing a type III secretion system to further
17 improve ABMT efficiency in cereals. An alternative approach is to deliver clustered
18 regularly interspaced short palindromic repeat (CRISPR)/CRISPR-associated
19 nuclease 9 (Cas9) ribonucleoproteins (RNPs) using biodegradable, polymeric
20 nanocomplexes via endocytosis-driven uptake into pollen grains (Gogoi et al., 2022).
21 This approach was used to knock out both alleles of the cloned stem rust *R* gene *Sr50*
22 in the homozygous wheat genotype *Gladius* + *Sr50*. The ability to improve ABMT
23 efficiency or provide an alternative to tissue culture has important implications for
24 future biotechnology applications in cereal crops recalcitrant to transformation.

25

1 **FUTURE PROSPECTS**

2 Rapid innovations, such as gene cassettes, gene editing, and enhanced
3 transformation efficiency, now more than ever offer the potential to improve crop
4 protection outcomes. Effective *R* gene combinations should, ideally, prioritize
5 mechanistic diversity to further enhance prospects for resistance durability. While
6 rarely durable individually, it is important to continue research on NLRs and their IDs
7 that act as pathogen effector decoys because NLRs may confer durable resistance
8 when used in polygene stacks. Naturally occurring loss-of-function mutations within
9 specific *S* genes involved in fungal biotrophic/parasitic habit represent promising
10 resistance mechanisms. One approach for fast-tracking *S* gene identification is to use
11 a mutational genomics approach in a diploid barley that is susceptible to most
12 biotrophic pathogens and amenable to transformation, such as the experimental
13 barley line Golden SusPtrit (Yeo et al., 2014). This approach would permit the
14 identification of recessive knockout mutations within genes involved in
15 susceptibility/biotrophy relative to those involved in ETI.

16 Although a large repertoire of wheat and barley rust and powdery mildew *R*
17 genes have been cloned, providing the basis for engineering powerful gene stacks
18 against these diseases in wheat and barley, our knowledge of the efficacy of many
19 cloned genes is still incomplete (Figure 2; Supplemental Tables 5-9). To maximize the
20 durability of resistance, it is important to incorporate multiple genes conferring
21 resistance against each existing pathogen isolate. Therefore, a more comprehensive
22 overview of the spectrum of resistance provided by the cloned *R* genes against
23 contemporary pathogen isolates from around the world is required. Generating this
24 knowledge using existing germplasm and pathogen resources is complicated by the

1 fact that the cloned genes are typically in different backgrounds containing other
2 effective *R* genes. These background genes can mask the resistance conferred by the
3 gene of interest. For example, wheat cv. Fielder, which is typically used as a
4 transformation line to confirm the function of cloned genes, likely contains stripe rust
5 *R* genes: *Yr6* (Chen and Line 1992), *Yr20* (Chen et al., 1995) and other catalogued *Sr*
6 and *Lr* genes yet to be determined thus masking the resistance conferred by any
7 cloned rust *R* gene against isolates containing corresponding *Avr* genes. Today,
8 researchers can take advantage of the low cost of DNA synthesis and the new
9 protocols for cultivar-independent transformation to incorporate 'all' cloned wheat and
10 barley rust and mildew *R* genes into universally susceptible cultivars, i.e., those
11 typically used as susceptible checks. The resulting true isogenic set could then be
12 shared with laboratories around the world for deep phenotyping. This approach would
13 provide the information required to exercise responsible gene stewardship by
14 permitting the judicious design of stacks that minimize the risk of selecting resistance-
15 evading pathogen variants (Figure 3).

16 One important consideration for deploying transgene cassettes in wheat is the
17 regulatory constraints and the socio-political opposition towards genetic modification
18 technologies in wheat-growing regions around the world (Wulff and Dhugga, 2018).
19 However, a genetically modified drought-tolerant wheat line containing the *Hb4*
20 transcription factor gene from sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*) was deregulated in
21 Argentina in August 2020 (González et al., 2018;
22 <https://investors.biocerescrops.com/news>), and the flour of this wheat was approved
23 in Brazil in November 2021 (<https://investors.biocerescrops.com>), the most important
24 wheat export market for Argentina. More recently, *Hb4* wheat was approved for use in
25 food and feed in the United States, Colombia, Australia, and New Zealand, thus
25

1 heralding a new era for commercial biotech wheat
2 (<https://investors.biocerescrops.com>). These developments will hopefully lower the
3 barrier for introducing additional transgenic traits, such as for disease resistance.

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12

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4

5 **Figure Legends**

6 **Figure 1.** Global wheat and barley production relative to demand and the effect of
7 pests and diseases on grain yield and end-use data. (A) Estimates of yield loss to
8 pests and diseases adapted from expert-based assessments of crop health (Savary
9 et al., 2019; Oerke and Dehne, 2004). (B) Worldwide wheat and barley production by
10 country in 2017 (FAO stats accessed on September 1st, 2022). (C) Trade
11 deficit/surplus calculated as the value in U.S. dollars between national demand and
12 production for wheat and barley. (D) End-use data for wheat and barley in 2020/21 as
13 a proportion of whole production. <https://www.igc.int/en/markets/marketinfo-sd.aspx>
14 (accessed on September 1st, 2022).

15 **Figure 2.** Efficacy of cloned resistance genes across agroecological zones.
16 (A) Map of the world divided into 17 agroecological zones representing different target
17 environments for wheat breeding. Adapted from Rajaram et al., (1994).
18 (B) Efficacy of the 31 cloned wheat stem rust, stripe rust and leaf rust resistance (*R*)
19 genes by agroecological zone. Colors from green to red represent virulence in the
20 pathogen population expressed as a percentage of isolates tested against a given *R*
21 gene that are virulent to this *R* gene. White indicates missing data (i.e., when less than
22 five isolates from an agroecological zone have been tested against a given *R* gene).
23 See Supplemental Tables 5-7 and 9 for further details.

1 (C) Genes that can be combined to create a polygene stack in wheat against rust and
2 powdery mildew pathogens. The stack was designed based on the most broad-
3 spectrum cloned *R* genes available for each respective disease in wheat across the
4 17 agroecological zone(s) (Supplemental Table 9). The stack has been conceptually
5 targeted to the same chromosome location to facilitate breeding and to ensure co-
6 inheritance of the major dominant *R* genes and the multi-disease *R* genes *Lr34* and
7 *Lr67*.

8 **Figure 3.** Creation and use of a wheat and barley isogenic library for determining the
9 efficacy of cloned *R* genes. Cloned rust *R* genes are transformed into lines universally
10 susceptible to either leaf rust (e.g., cv. Thatcher), stripe rust (e.g., cv. Avocet S), and
11 stem rust (e.g., cv. Morocco). Genetically stable and publicly available homozygous
12 isogenic lines can be shared and phenotyped around the world to determine the
13 regional and worldwide efficacy of each gene to inform judicious stacking and
14 deployment.

15

1 **Supplemental Tables**

2 **Supplemental Table 1.** Wheat and barley grain production and trade by country.

3 **Supplemental Table 2.** Wheat and barley grain end use data.

4 **Supplemental Table 3.** List of cloned wheat and barley *R* genes and their mode of
5 inheritance (adapted from Uauy et al., 2017, and Yu et al., 2022).

6 **Supplemental Table 4.** List of cloned *Avr* effector genes from wheat and barley
7 pathogens (adapted from Hafeez et al., 2021, and Sánchez-Martín and Keller, 2021).

8 **Supplemental Table 5.** Efficacy of cloned wheat stem rust *R* genes.

9 **Supplemental Table 6.** Efficacy of cloned wheat stripe rust *R* genes.

10 **Supplemental Table 7.** Efficacy of cloned wheat leaf rust *R* genes.

11 **Supplemental Table 8.** Efficacy of cloned wheat powdery mildew *R* genes.

12 **Supplemental Table 9.** Efficacy summary for cloned wheat rust and powdery mildew
13 *R* genes.

14

15

A PRODUCTION

B PRODUCTION BY COUNTRY (WHEAT LEFT / BARLEY RIGHT)

C DIFFERENCE BETWEEN NATIONAL DEMAND AND PRODUCTION

D END USE

1

2 **Figure 1**

3

4

5

1

2 **Figure 2**

3

1

2 **Figure 3**